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Pathways to eradication: a quantitative exploration of malaria trajectories in Africa to 2050

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Pathways to eradication: a quantitative exploration of malaria trajectories in Africa to 2050

1. Introduction

There is a broad consensus that the eradication of malaria in Africa will require, at a minimum, multiple decades to achieve. Over that timeframe, it is probable that many facets of the continent we are familiar with today will be substantively different. Socioeconomic development, climate change, geopolitics and many other driving factors will likely result in widespread and potentially dramatic changes to the natural and built environment. This is important in the context of malaria eradication because malaria transmission, and our ability to reduce or prevent it, are intrinsically linked to the biophysical and human systems within which transmission occurs. It is plausible that the inadvertent effect on malaria of this changing background may be as, or even more, important to our eventual success or failure than is the deliberate impact of control and elimination efforts themselves. A plan for malaria eradication that assumes these 'background' conditions will remain static is therefore unlikely to be optimal.

By acknowledging that change will happen, however, and by considering the possible nature and magnitude of that change, we can inform the following key questions in the debate on malaria eradication.

- (i) Compared to conditions today, what are the key changes to natural and human systems that will impact most on malaria transmission in Africa? Will these help or hinder our efforts? How will impacts vary across the continent?
- (ii) Given these impacts, what are plausible trajectories and geographical patterns of malaria transmission reduction and elimination against which we can plan and then measure progress towards defined goals?
- (iii) Where are likely to be the regions of Africa that pose the most stubborn challenge - eliminating last and constituting a final hurdle to ultimate eradication?

In this study we present a quantitative analysis that attempts to shed light on these questions.

2. Methods

The work uses as a starting point our best understanding of malaria risk in Africa in the present day and how it is mediated by the natural and human environments, and then links this to projected changes in those environments over the coming decades to predict impacts on malaria and

implications for eradication. We have built an analytical framework to generate maps of malaria risk in Africa for the benchmark years of 2030 and 2050. The year 2050 is chosen to represent a notional target date for global eradication, although it is stressed that this choice is somewhat arbitrary – providing a point of reference for analysis rather than a policy-oriented declaration of intent. The year 2030 is included as a key staging-post against which progress to eventual eradication can be evaluated. We represent malaria transmission in this analysis using parasite rate (PR), which measures infection prevalence - the fraction of individuals with a patent blood-stage malaria infection at a given point in time. PR is the unit for which data are most readily available and is therefore widely understood and interpretable.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for analysis. Blue, orange and green boxes denote input data, modelling steps, and output, respectively.

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram summarising the conceptual approach taken in this analysis to generate predicted maps of future malaria. The main steps are now described in summary, with additional details provided in Annex A1.

i) Characterising the relationship between environmental conditions, intervention coverage, and malaria transmission. The Malaria Atlas Project (MAP) maintains exhaustive databases of three types of relevant spatially-referenced data spanning the years 2000-2018: (a) malariometric data including around 50,000 independent observations of PR at defined point locations across Africa; (b) data on ITN, IRS and ACT coverage at point locations and across national and subnational regions; (c) gridded geospatial data characterising the natural and human ‘micro-environment’. The latter data span a broad range of variables including metrics of rainfall, temperature, vegetation density, land cover classes, population density, urban areas, and housing quality, and are available as continent-wide gridded data surfaces where each grid cell represents an area of approximately 5x5 km. These three classes of data were combined in a Bayesian geostatistical model that allowed the empirical

relationships between the environmental and intervention variables and PR to be characterised. The particular model structure used included a 'stacked generalisation' component which, in essence, allows these multivariate relationships to be defined in a highly flexible way – relationships can be non-linear and interact with each other to allow their complexity to be captured appropriately without over-fitting. This geostatistical model is described in more detail in Annex A1.1.

ii) Creating future-projected spatial data on plausible environmental conditions in 2030 and 2050 under different scenarios of global change. The second step was to create a suite of equivalent micro-environmental data that represents plausible future conditions in 2030 and 2050. Predicting global change in a precise way this far into the future is, of course, not feasible because so many future events and large-scale trends are unknown. However, gaining a broad understanding of possible future trends in macro-scale factors (for example population growth, global atmospheric carbon concentration, and Gross Domestic Product (GDP)), and how these may propagate across a wider set of interlinked climatic, biological and societal outcomes, is useful and has been a key goal of scientists considering climate change impacts and mitigation under the auspices of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). This body of work has given rise to a set of five defined future scenarios termed Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) that, collectively, present a set of internally consistent narratives on future macro-scale global trends. Our approach has been to obtain or generate future-projected geospatial surfaces on the key micro-environmental variables (i.e. those that act most directly on malaria) that reflect changes in macro-scale factors predicted in the SSPs. Many such surfaces have already been developed by other researchers working in climatology or related fields – these include surfaces of changes in population, urban areas, temperature, rainfall and key land cover classes. Other important variables were not available and, for these, we developed our own modelling frameworks to predict future-projected data surfaces where trends were driven by relevant variables as predicted at national or regional scale within the SSP. These future-projected surfaces are described in more detail in Annex A1.2. The full SSP framework consists of five distinct scenarios. In this work we evaluated two: SSP2 (representing a central tendency or 'middle of the road' vision of the future) and SSP5 (representing the future world under a pathway of 'conventional development' with high atmospheric carbon concentrations).

iii) Using the relationships defined in (i) to predict maps of malaria in Africa in 2030 and 2050 under the different environmental scenarios defined in (ii), holding interventions at contemporary levels. The fitted geospatial model defined in the first step, with the defined environment-malaria relationships, was rerun to generate maps of PR in 2030 and 2050. This was achieved by replacing

the contemporary geospatial micro-environmental input data with the equivalent surfaces projected to those future years, while holding input data on intervention coverage constant at 2017 levels.

iv) Predicting further maps for 2030 and 2050 that reflect enhanced coverage of current tools and innovation of new ones. To flexibly represent the possible future impact of changes to contemporary malaria control - whether by increasing coverage of existing tools or widespread application of potential new, or currently nascent, tools – we used a mathematical transmission model. The EMOD (Epidemiological MODelling software) model is a modular, individual-based model developed by the Institute for Disease Modelling which explicitly simulates vector life and feeding cycles, transmission, within-host parasite dynamics, human demographics and movement and antimalarial interventions. We developed a novel geographically-varying implementation of EMOD that allowed locally realistic climate, seasonality and vector species bionomics to be captured. Further details are provided in Annex A1.3. We then simulated the impact on PR of a range of different future intervention scenarios. These intervention scenarios were not intended to be exhaustive but rather to reflect alternative strategic, financial, and technological pathways that would yield very different levels of effective malaria control, as follows.

‘Contemporary coverage’ . Under this scenario, future malaria control is simply maintained at the levels seen in 2017 (the most recent year for which we have reliable data). This scenario is useful because it allows us to evaluate whether eradication can be achieved without increases in coverage or introduction of new tools. Additionally, it allows the effect of changing environmental factors to be evaluated independently, while holding interventions constant.

‘Scale-up of current tools’. Under this group of scenarios, no new malaria control tools are introduced, but those currently in widespread use (namely insecticide treated bednets, ITNs; indoor residual spraying, IRS; antimalarial treatment with Artemisinin-based combination therapy, ACT) are increased to represent improved levels of operational coverage. Numerous variants are included within this scenario group to explore the interacting effects of different coverage levels across the intervention types. A coverage level of 80% is used to represent a likely maximum achievable level for each intervention. The specific definitions of coverage for each intervention are discussed more in Annex A1.3.

‘Innovation of new tools’. This diverse group of scenarios evaluates the possible impact of a variety of new vector control, vaccines, and drug classes used in conjunction (or, where appropriate, replacing) existing tools. The precise specification of these new tools in the analysis is discussed in more detail in Annex A1.3.

Results

Figure 2 shows predicted endemicity across Africa in 2030 and 2050 under the initial scenario where interventions are held constant at current (2017) levels. The combined effects of the changing environmental factors is predicted to yield significant declines in *PfPR* by 2030 and further declines by 2050. By 2050, most areas experiencing high transmission today (e.g. *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ > 30%) are projected to fall below *PfPR* of 10%, while currently low transmission regions tend to approach zero. Pockets of higher transmission remain in West and South Eastern Africa.

Figure 2. Projected future impact on malaria endemicity of the changing environment. Maps show *Plasmodium falciparum* infection prevalence (2-10 year olds) for the present day (A), and projected for the years 2030 (B) and 2050 (C). In both projections, malaria intervention coverage was held constant to 2017 levels, and both relate to the SSP2 pathway.

Figure 3 shows the corresponding level of malaria morbidity associated with these projections (tabulated in full in Table 1). With current intervention levels maintained, by 2030 we project annual case incidence to fall from 207 per 1000 persons at risk today to 174/1000, and to 130/1000 by 2050. The declines in incidence rate, however are largely counteracted by projected growth in underlying populations at risk, such that overall numbers of malaria cases are projected to remain at around 200 million in 2030 and 2050.

Figure 4 shows the projected effect of changing environmental factors by 2030 and 2050 in addition to the scale up of existing malaria control tools. Achieving and maintain effective coverage of both ITNs and ACTs at 80% (Figure 4 A,B) yield further significant declines in *PfPR* above those due to environmental effects alone. By 2050, remaining high transmission pockets seen in Figure 2C have declined to generally less than 5% *PfPR* and many parts of Africa are at zero. Further addition of IRS

Table 1. Projected future incidence rate and cases in Africa in 2030 and 2050 under different intervention scenarios. All projections relate to the SSP2 pathway.

Intervention level	Incidence (cases/1000)			Cases (millions)		
	2017	2030	2050	2017	2030	2050
Current intervention levels	206.7	172.9	130.0	200.54	197.68	202.96
Increase current tools to 80% (ITNs, ACTs)		28.6	17.4		32.74	27.20
Increase current tools to 80% (ITNs, ACTs, IRS)		11.5	7.1		13.10	11.01
Add new tools (case management with DHA+PQ)		5.0	2.8		5.71	4.38
Add new tools (monoclonal antibodies)		8.6	5.0		9.82	7.77
Add new tools (pre-erythrocytic vaccine)		9.9	5.9		11.28	9.27
Add new tools (transmission blocking vaccine)		6.2	3.4		7.04	5.32

at 80% (Figure 4A and 4B) leads to elimination from most of the continent with scattered pockets of *PfPR* between 1-5% across mainly West and South Eastern Africa. Figure 3 shows the corresponding impacts on morbidity. Under the 80% ITN, IRS, ACT scenario, case incidence by 2050 is projected to fall from 207/1000 today to 7.1/1000 (Table 1). Despite these declines, the pockets of remaining transmission are projected to still yield some 11 million cases annually (Table 1).

Figure 3. Projected changes in malaria incidence in Africa under different intervention scenarios. Plots show projected change in (A) incidence rate and (B) number of cases between the present day, 2030 and 2050. All projections relate to the SSP2 pathway.

Increases in current tools (ITN 80%; ACT 80%)

Increases in current tools (ITN 80%; ACT 80%; IRS 80%)

Figure 4. Projected future impact on malaria endemicity of the changing environment and increased coverage of existing malaria control. Maps show *Plasmodium falciparum* infection prevalence (2-10 year olds) for the years 2030 (A, C) and 2050 (B, D) under enhanced coverage of existing malaria control tools: 80% ITN and ACT coverage (A,B) and 80% ITN, ACT and IRS coverage (B,D). All projections relate to the SSP2 pathway.

Figure 5 shows the projected additional impact of introducing new malaria control tools in addition to the scale up of scale up of current tools, and in combination with changing environmental factors by 2030 and 2050. When compared to the impact of high coverage of existing tools (e.g. Figure 4D), the additional use of these new drug and vaccine-based interventions appears to yield little further reductions in the geographical extent of sustained transmission by 2050. Further impacts can be seen, however, in morbidity levels (Table 1). Replacement of current ACTs with DHA-PQ for case management, for example, is projected to take incidence rates in 2050 from 7.1/1000 (under 80% coverage of ITN, ACT, IRS) to 2.8/1000.

Monoclonal Antibodies

Figure 5. Projected future impact on malaria endemicity of the changing environment, increased coverage of existing malaria control, and addition of innovative new tools. Maps show *Plasmodium falciparum* infection prevalence (2-10 year olds) for the years 2030 (A, C, E G) and 2050 (B, D, F, H). All projections included enhanced coverage of existing malaria control tools (80% coverage with ITN, ACT and IRS) and additionally large-scale deployment of: a monoclonal antibody-based vaccine (A,B); a pre-erythrocytic vaccine (C,D); treatment with Dihydroartemisinin+piperazine as a replacement for existing ACTs (E,F); A transmission blocking vaccine (G,H). All projections relate to the SSP2 pathway.

Pre-erythrocytic vaccine

Case management with Dihydroartemisinin + piperazine

Transmission-blocking vaccine

Further results are shown in Annex A2 detailing our projections under the alternative future conditions associated with the SSP5 'conventional development' pathway. This scenario was included to assess the sensitivity of overall results to the choice of SSP. The maps presented for 2030 and 2050 under current intervention levels (Figure A11), scale up of existing tools (Figure A12) and introduction of new tools (Figure A13) all display considerable similarity to the main results shown here for SSP2.

Discussion

Predicting the future is, inevitably, a hazardous undertaking, and this is especially so for a phenomenon as complex and diverse as malaria endemicity across Africa. Nevertheless, the framework developed here brings together a large collection of contemporary data on malaria, its control, and the environmental factors which mediate it most strongly, and combines these with the standard IPCC descriptions of future global change scenarios to infer how those changes may impact malaria alone and in combination with control efforts.

Our analysis suggests that the effects on malaria of changing human and biophysical environments will be varied but, overall, have substantial positive impacts that will assist efforts to eradicate the disease over a multiple decade timescale. Our models of intervention impact suggest that in combination with the changing environment existing control tools could, if coverage were maximised to ambitious but operationally feasible levels, reduce transmission dramatically to small pockets scattered across west, central and south east Africa. Despite the projected large declines, however, we do not predict that environmental change and the maximised use of current tools, whether alone or in combination, would result in the complete elimination of malaria from Africa. We project that the addition of a variety of innovative new vaccines or drugs makes only modest further impact. This is likely to reflect the already very high treatment coverage under our base scenario (80% effective treatment with ACTs), leaving less scope for further impact with such tools. We did not explore innovative vector control such as ATSBs and it is plausible that tools targeting outdoor biting or larval habitats would be well suited to addressing pockets of remaining risk where residual transmission plays an important role.

Our approach makes the necessarily strong assumption that the nature of the relationship between the environment and malaria transmission will remain constant though time, conditional on intervention levels. This may not be justified if the transmission system itself changes – for example if a new *anopheles* vector were to be introduced to a region with very different bionomics to those it displaces.

We have attempted to build a rich analytical framework that considers many factors potentially acting on malaria transmission but, inevitably, others were omitted due to gaps in data or conceptual understanding. We do not address the potential impacts of mass human movement for example, but recognise this may occur on unprecedented scales and have commensurate impacts on malaria dynamics. We chose to assess the potential impact of interventions under specified levels of effective coverage. This implicitly ignores the challenges of achieving such coverage, and the reality that this would likely not be achieved uniformly. We chose to exclude analysis of the deleterious effects of emerging resistance in vectors or parasites, but acknowledge that achieving impact with current tools is critically reliant on their maintained efficacy. We use a relatively simple conceptualisation of the mechanism and efficacy of new tools which, inevitably, have far less empirical data on their true performance in the field, in particular in combination with existing tools. We concluded that these new drug or vaccine treatments would have limited additional impact when added to scenarios with already very high ITN, IRS, and ACT coverage, but this does not imply that their impact could not be much greater in situations where existing tools are deployed less optimally.

Our results are built around the visions of future change encapsulated in the IPCC SSP/RCP framework. That framework is also, of course, founded on many interacting assumptions about future change and must be interpreted as a set of plausible narratives rather than a precise forecast. Some of the largest impact of environmental change in our models stem from socioeconomic development and associated urbanization, physical infrastructure and housing modernisation. As such our findings rely heavily on the central projections within the SSP/RCP framework of rising GDP in most African nations over coming decades. We have focused our analysis on two of the five SSP scenarios (SSP2 and SSP5) which, in part, reflects the lesser availability of geospatial data products built from the other three SSPs.

Nevertheless, under some of these alternative future narratives, it is plausible that our conclusions would differ.

Despite these various caveats, this analysis represents the first formal attempt to quantify the possible impacts of global megatrends on malaria in Africa and implications for eradication in the coming decades. Global trends of environmental change must be considered in any efforts to plan eradication efforts over multiple decades, as their effects will likely be significant over those timescales. If current projections of socioeconomic development on the continent come to pass, associated changes to the built environment may well be beneficial and assist the push to eradicate. The changing climate will likely have more varied effects, acting to both suppress or amplify transmission depending on the local context. Finally, it is clear that maintaining the status quo of malaria control will not be enough, despite potential assistance from megatrend impacts. However, while much more study is needed, this broad brush analysis does suggest, that the changing environment coupled with enhanced coverage of current and new tools could precipitously reduce transmission across the continent and bring eradication within reach.